

TREASoURcE

D8.4 Website

WP no and title	WP8 Communication and dissemination
Lead Beneficiary	CLIC Innovation Ltd (CLIC)
Responsible Author(s)	Kaisa Simola (CLIC)
Contributor(s)	Anna Tenhunen-Lunkka (VTT)
	All partners

This document contains the description of the project website that has been designed for the TREASoURcE project (Grant Agreement No. 101059491). The design and content of the website have been developed by CLIC Innovation in collaboration with the whole consortium. This document presents a detailed description of the website communication strategy, structure and design, navigability, and content development process.

Project Details			
Project acronym	TREASoURcE	Start / Duration	June 2022 / 48 months
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-CIRCBIO-01-01 – Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)'s circular systemic solutions	Grant Agreement No	101059491
Type of Action	Innovation Action (IA)	Coordinator	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd
Contact person	Anna Tenhunen-Lunkka, anna.tenhunen-lunkka@vtt.fi		
Website	https://treasource.eu/		

Deliverable Details			
Deliverable No	D8.4		
Deliverable Name	Website		
Work Package	WP8 Communication and dissemination		
Dissemination level	PU - Public	Type	DEC - Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.
Due Date (M)	M3 (31.8.2022)	Submission date	31.8.2022
Lead Beneficiary	CLIC Innovation Ltd (CLIC)	Responsible Author	Kaisa Simola, kaisa.simola@clinnovation.fi

Deliverable Contributors				
	Name	Organisation	Role / Title	E-mail
Deliverable leader	Kaisa Simola	CLIC	Communication and Dissemination Manager, WP8 Leader	kaisa.simola@clinnovation.fi
Contributing Author(s)	Anna Tenhunen-Lunkka	VTT	Project Coordinator	anna.tenhunen-lunkka@vtt.fi
	All partners			
Reviewer(s)	Anna Tenhunen-Lunkka	VTT	Project Coordinator	anna.tenhunen-lunkka@vtt.fi
Final review and quality approval	Anna Tenhunen-Lunkka	VTT	Project Coordinator	anna.tenhunen-lunkka@vtt.fi

Document History			
Date	Version	Name	Changes
23/08/2022	1	First version	
29/08/2022	2	Second version for final review	Corrections by Project Coordinator included <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Executive Summary added - Lists of Figures and Tables added
30/8/2022	3	Final version	Final formatting of the document

Table of Contents

Acronyms and abbreviations.....	3
Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Target audiences	5
3. Measuring impact.....	6
4. Website design and launch.....	8

List of Figures

Figure 1. Homepage.....	11
-------------------------	----

List of Tables

Table 1. Target groups, objectives and content.....	5
Table 2. Website-related KPIs	7
Table 3. Website structure	8

Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Full name
BT	Business Tampere
CLIC	CLIC Innovation Ltd
D	Deliverable Report
ECO	ECO STOR AS
EKOF	Ekokumppanit Oy (EcoFellows)
Frstad	Fredrikstad kommune
FVH	Forum Virium Helsinki Oy
GA	Grant Agreement
GD	GreenDelta GMBH
MTK	The Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners
PF	Polyfuels Group AB (Previously known as Green Ideas Group GIG)
SDU	Syddansk Universitet
SINTEF	SINTEF AS / SINTEF Energy
TalTech	Tallinna Tehnikaülikool
TARTU	Tartu Linn (Tartu City)
TLN	Tallinna Linn (City of Tallinn)
TOPSOE	Topsoe AS
VIKEN	Viken Fylkeskommune
VTT	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd
WP	Work package

Executive Summary

This document contains the description of the website designed for the TREASoURcE project, accessible at <https://treasource.eu/>. The design and launching of TREASoURcE website is part of the Task 8.1, *Dissemination and communication plan, channels and materials*, within the Communication and dissemination work package (WP8). The design of the website has been developed by CLIC Innovation in collaboration with the whole consortium.

Operational as of Month 3, the project website has been created to serve as a central information point for the various stakeholders and media; it has been designed to be the main information repository for the project, its objectives, results and findings, and all activities related to its developments and progress. All communication materials and any other non-confidential documentation related to TREASoURcE will be either published on or linked to the project website.

The content and messages incorporated have been defined with the purpose of reaching different audiences, including industry, citizens and communities, scientific community, and policymakers with the objective to benefit the project results. The website will be provided with information matching the particular interests and needs of each target group and subgroup. It has been designed to support intuitive navigation to help visitors to find content that is pertinent to them. The website has a key role in communication and dissemination of the results and findings as well as in creating the overall impact of the project. To generate the needed statistical data and to monitor the performance, the TREASoURcE website is using Matomo Analytics.

The TREASoURcE website has been designed for a user-friendly experience with a layout that enhances the visibility of the project brand. The modern layout follows the overall look and feel set by the developed project visual identity: logo, colours, typography, graphic elements, and images.

The site is not a static tool. It will be managed by CLIC, further developed, and updated regularly during the project lifetime. All partners will contribute to the content creation, share their progress and other activities. The website will remain accessible for two years after the project's completion.

1. Introduction

This deliverable contains the description of the project website that has been designed for the TREASoURcE project. The design and launching of TREASoURcE website is part of the Task 8.1, *Dissemination and communication plan, channels and materials*, within the Communication and dissemination work package (WP8). Operational as of Month 3, the project website has been created to serve as a central information point for the various stakeholders and media. It has been designed to be the main information repository for the project, its objectives, results and findings, and all activities related to its developments and progress. All communication materials and any other non-confidential documentation related to the TREASoURcE project will be either published on or linked to the project website. Project partner CLIC is responsible for managing and updating the website as well as for coordinating the content creation with all partners.

The communication strategy was designed around key questions that external visitors to the website might have:

- **WHY** - Highlight the background, importance, and purpose of the project, which goes from the very specific targets of each key value chain to the overall objective of enhancing the transition to and uptake of circular economy solutions in the TREASoURcE territories and beyond.
- **WHAT** - Provide a description and approach to the project.
- **WHO** - Present the consortium working to achieve these objectives.
- **HOW** - Describe TREASoURcE progress along the project's development.

All this information appears or will appear on the website. The content and messages incorporated have been defined with the purpose of reaching different audiences, including general public, scientific community, industry, and policymakers with the objective to benefit the project results.

2. Target audiences

The website will be provided with information matching the particular interests and needs of each target group and subgroup. Clear headings and subheadings support intuitive navigation to help visitors to find content that is pertinent to them. Target groups, objectives and content are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Target groups, objectives and content

Target group	Objectives and content
Market / Industrial stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Generate interest among early adopters.- Wide outreach and cooperation with value chain actors in the three key value chains.- Promote uptake of individual project results.- Get feedback from target audience, provide solutions to perceived risks.- Share success stories, foster sustainability in the sector.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase awareness of the capabilities and uses of the TREASoURcE Replication Handbook. - Support successful replication of the identified CE solutions.
Citizens and Communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness raising campaigns with various activities engaging citizens among other stakeholders (see D8.1) - Educate and deepen understanding of the role and possibilities of citizens and communities on systemic CE solutions. - Inspire for changing everyday life practices. - Fostering acceptance of recycled products/products with recycled content. - Illustrative and didactic graphic and video materials.
Scientific community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inform about the scientific project results. - Education and training of new experts in CE. - Sharing results, knowledge diffusion with other experts, opening further research paths. - Getting feedback and new contacts with academic and nonacademic experts and groups working in CE.
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Suggest improvements to overcome local, national and EU-level regulatory barriers preventing CE transition and scalability. - Foster the replication and the public-private link. - Increase awareness of the capabilities and uses of the TREASoURcE Replication Handbook.
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness campaigns aiming for a wide coverage in TREASoURcE countries and regions - Potential of the circular economy in Europe for creating wealth and jobs. - Usefulness of EU R&D and initiatives like CCRI. - Illustrative and didactic graphic and video materials.
Other CCRI and CE projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure synergies and enable wide exploitation to enhance the use of new knowledge in CE beyond the project.

TREASoURcE has ambitious targets with regard to engaging in an active two-way exchange with various stakeholder groups via activities related to stakeholder engagement and key value chain demonstrations (WPs 2-5). A full description of target groups, key messages, channels and tools of communication and dissemination is presented in D8.1, Communication and Dissemination Plan.

3. Measuring impact

As stated above, the project website has an important and central role in communication and dissemination of the results and findings of TREASoURcE. The overall impact will be measured through a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Table 2 presents an overview of the website-related KPIs set for the whole project duration (48 months).

Table 2. Website-related KPIs

Means	Target audience	KPI
Website	All stakeholders	N° visits: 5 000
Newsletter	Industry, academia, public bodies, decision makers	N° of publications: 8 N° of subscribers: 500 N° of views: 2 000
Press releases	Media, all stakeholders and general public	N° of publications: 4-8 N° of contacted media: 500
Promotional materials: presentations, leaflets, brochures, etc.	Consortium, all stakeholders	N° of publications: 5-8 online versions N° of downloads: 500
Social media	Media, general public, value chain actors, industry, academia, public bodies	N° of followers: 200 (per channel) N° of posts: 80 (per channel)
Videos	All stakeholders	N° of videos: 2-4 N° of views: 300
Blog posts	Industry, academia, public and funding bodies, decision makers, media, citizens	N° of publications: 15 N° of views: 800
Podcast series	Industry, academia, public and funding bodies, decision makers, media, citizens	N° of publications: 4-8 N° of listening sessions: 250
Scientific publications	Academia, Industry	N° of papers: 5-10 peer-reviewed papers

A full set of communication and dissemination KPIs is presented in D8.1, Communication and Dissemination Plan.

3.1. Website analytics and GDPR compliance

To generate the needed statistical data and to extract analytics on the performance, TREASoURcE website is using Matomo Analytics. The tool is included in the WordPress content management system and operated by CLIC. Statistical data will be collected and analysed to identify any needed changes and to optimise the user experience on the website. The same data will be used for reporting the progress of the website-related KPIs.

The initial plan was to use Google Analytics on the TREASoURcE website. However, the data management and GDPR compliance matters were discussed within the consortium during the online kick-off on June 14, 2022. Following the discussion, the consortium decided to replace Google Analytics with Matomo Analytics due to GDPR-related concerns.

The website's Privacy Policy and Cookie Policy are available on the website and will be kept up to date. The website footer has clear and visible links to access this information.

4. Website design and launch

The TREASoURcE website is accessible on <https://treasource.eu/>. The domain name was reserved on the second day of the project, June 2nd, 2022, alongside with the creation of the project e-mail address, info@treasource.eu. The [.eu](https://treasource.eu/) domain was chosen to emphasize the European aspect of the project.

The website was published by M3 (August 16, 2022). The launch date was deliberately set to coincide with the face-to-face project kick-off in order to present the new website to the partners and to promote it. The website will be managed and updated regularly during the project lifetime and it will remain accessible for two years after the project’s completion. The website is presented in English as it is the official project language set by the Grant Agreement.

4.1. Website structure and content

The TREASoURcE project website is characterized by its easy navigability, simplicity and user-friendly features. Intended to be an informative website, and according to the project’s needs to update information, this organisation or internet architecture allows the different audiences to learn more about the project.

On the menu, the following sections have been created: About, Systemic CE solutions, Publications, Events, News and Contact. The entire website structure is presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Website structure

HOME	ABOUT	SYSTEMIC CE SOLUTIONS	PUBLICATIONS	EVENTS	NEWS	CONTACT
	PROJECT	STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT DEMOS	PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS	WORKSHOPS	NEWS	
	PARTNERS	CIRCULAR PLASTICS	REPORTS	CAMPAIGNS	BLOG	
		CIRCULAR BATTERIES	PRESS RELEASES	EVENT TESTERS	SOCIAL MEDIA	
		BIO-BASED SIDE AND WASTE STREAMS	NEWSLETTERS			

As the project is still in its early stages, some of the pages and sections shown in the table above are not currently visible to visitors due to a lack of appropriate content. They will be reactivated once relevant content is created and can be fed on the website.

The website encompasses a variety of materials that allow a successful communication and dissemination amongst the partners and towards the various target audiences. The ‘About’ submenu comprises two (2) subsections to introduce the project: Project and Partners. The first one includes also four (4) subsections: Objectives, Impact, Methodology and Circular Cities and Regions Initiative. They briefly present the value proposition of the TREASoURcE project including pictures, graphics, figures and messages to let the audience understand what the project is about and why it is innovative and

marketable. The Partners section includes a description of each organisation involved in the project with contact e-mails, links to their website and social media. A partner map is foreseen to be included in this section to better illustrate the partner location and the territorial and regional aspect of the project.

The 'Systemic CE solutions' section introduces the project approach with the various demonstrations in more detail. The four (4) subsections 'Stakeholder engagement demos', 'Circular plastics', 'Circular batteries' and 'Bio-based side and waste streams' correspond each to a certain demonstration or a group of demonstrations. These sections will be further developed in cooperation with the corresponding key value chain or stakeholder engagement demos once more information is available (e.g., on demo sites, stakeholder engagement campaigns, etc.)

On the 'Publications' submenu, there are two (4) subsections: Promotional materials, Reports, Press releases and Newsletters. These will be used to organise all the produced materials and documents to be easily found and available for open use by any interested stakeholders. Currently, only the last two subsections are visible on the website. Once promotional materials or public project reports will be produced and available, these sections will be reactivated. Public deliverables and reports will be uploaded once they are approved.

The 'Events' submenu is divided into three (3) subsections: Workshops, Campaigns and Event testers. The Events section is crucial and will be widely used to communicate about the upcoming project events and activities, especially around the planned demonstrations and related campaigns.

The 'News' submenu contains three (3) subsections: News, Blog and Social media. News related to the TREASoURcE project will be posted regularly and will revolve around topics such as: the objectives of the project, the progress of the work carried out, upcoming events and workshops, publications, released newsletters or blog posts, etc. An embedded social media feed will figure in the last subsection.

The 'Contact' section presents the general email address of the project info@treasource.eu that is managed by the TREASoURcE Communications team (CLIC), Project coordinator and Communication and Dissemination Manager's contact details, newsletter subscription form and a contact form for interested stakeholders to use. The messages sent via the contact form will be received in the project info mail info@treasource.eu.

Social media icons (Twitter and LinkedIn) appear in the header and the footer. The links to access the website Privacy Policy and Cookie Policy are placed in the footer.

The site is not a static tool. It will be further developed, and modifications can be made at any time per the consortium's request and verification with the Project coordinator. CLIC will regularly update and maintain it, playing a proactive role in checking with partners for the latest news to ensure the regularity and timeliness of the information flow. All partners will contribute to the content creation, share their progress and other activities as part of Tasks 8.1 and 8.2.

Content resulting from project outcomes and other activities will be published on a regular basis. All partners will contribute to this by sharing their progress and activities with CLIC, who will then consolidate the information and proceed to the website update.

4.2. Design and layout

The TREASoURcE website has been designed for a user-friendly experience with a layout that enhances the visibility of the project brand. The modern layout follows the overall look and feel set by the developed project visual identity: logo, colours, typography, graphic elements, and images (see D8.1 for detailed description of the visual identity).

The layout is based on storytelling principles that guides the site visitor through the TREASoURcE story using images, graphics, and key appealing messages that express the value proposition of the project's technologies, methodologies, and identity.

The TREASoURcE website has been designed to respond to different user's behaviours and environments based on device, screen size and resolution, platform, and orientation. The website is responsive to adapt to a variety of devices and screen sizes, such as computers, laptops, smartphones, and tablets.

Figure 1 shows a screenshot of the homepage to get an idea of the overall look and feel of the website. It is intended as an example while the best way to get an idea of the website in its entirety is to visit it at www.treasure.eu.

Boosting circularity and initiating systemic change

TREASoURcE aims to initiate systemic change by developing systemic circular economy solutions in cities and regions for currently underutilised or unused plastic waste, end-of-life electric vehicle batteries and bio-based waste and side streams. Implementing these solutions together with companies, societies (including citizens, consumers, communities and regional actors) and experts in the field is expected to significantly increase product and material circulation in the Nordic and Baltic Sea Regions.

Circular Economy

Climate change, environmental degradation and loss of biodiversity are major global threats that require urgent collaborative actions across industry, sectors, cities and regions, communities and citizens. Half of total greenhouse gas emissions and more than 90 % of biodiversity loss come from resource extraction and processing. Global consumption of materials, especially biomass, fossil fuels, metals and minerals are expected to double by 2060 and annual waste generation is estimated to increase by 70 % by 2060.

The combination of the cities and regions will enable large reach and bigger impact and boost the replicability and scalability potential of the circular economy solutions. The systemic circular economy solutions support the regions in introducing circular economy practices to their citizens and businesses to help decouple from fossil virgin resources and excess raw material consumption, increase resilience (self-sufficiency, value chain security, environment, and nature), decrease greenhouse gas emissions, and contribute to climate neutral economies.

Figure 1. Homepage